

Sleep

Veillez remplir le questionnaire ci-dessous.

Merci !

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- 1) How long do you usually take to fall asleep?
- About 10 minutes or less
 - Between 11 and 20 minutes
 - Between 21 and 30 minutes
 - Between 31 and 40 minutes
 - Between 41 and 50 minutes
 - Between 51 and 60 minutes
 - About 60 minutes or more
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- 2) If you go to school the day after, when you are in your bedroom at night, you usually use...
- Books
 - A radio
 - A TV
 - A music player (CD, MP3, Ipod, ...)
 - A game console (including mobile console)
 - A mobile phone with no internet connection
 - A mobile phone with an internet connection
 - A computer with no internet connection
 - A computer with an internet connection
 - I don't do anything
(You can check several boxes)
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- 3) What time do you usually fall asleep when you go to school the day after?
- About 6PM or before
 - About 6.30PM
 - About 7PM
 - About 7.30PM
 - About 8PM
 - About 8.30PM
 - About 9PM
 - About 9.30PM
 - About 10PM
 - About 10.30PM
 - About 11PM
 - About 11.30PM
 - About midnight (12AM)
 - About 12.30AM
 - About 1AM
 - About 1.30AM
 - About 2AM
 - About 2.30AM
 - About 3AM or later
(Between 6PM and 3AM)
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- 4) What time do you usually wake up when you go to school in the morning?
- About 4AM or before
 - About 4.30AM
 - About 5AM
 - About 5.30AM
 - About 6AM
 - About 6.30AM
 - About 7AM
 - About 7.30AM
 - About 8AM
 - About 8.30AM
 - About 9AM
 - About 9.30AM
 - About 10AM or after
(Between 4AM and 10AM)

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- 5) If you don't go to school the day after, when you are in your bedroom at night, you usually use...
- Books
 - A radio
 - A TV
 - A music player (CD, MP3, Ipod, ...)
 - A game console (including mobile console)
 - A mobile phone with no internet connection
 - A mobile phone with an internet connection
 - A computer with no internet connection
 - A computer with an internet connection
 - I don't do anything
- (You can check several boxes)
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- 6) What time do you usually fall asleep when you don't go to school the day after?
- About 6PM or before
 - About 6.30PM
 - About 7PM
 - About 7.30PM
 - About 8PM
 - About 8.30PM
 - About 9PM
 - About 9.30PM
 - About 10PM
 - About 10.30PM
 - About 11PM
 - About 11.30PM
 - About midnight (12AM)
 - About 12.30AM
 - About 1AM
 - About 1.30AM
 - About 2AM
 - About 2.30AM
 - About 3AM or later
- (Between 6PM and 3AM)
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- 7) What time do you usually wake up when you don't go to school in the morning?
- About 4AM or before
 - About 4.30AM
 - About 5AM
 - About 5.30AM
 - About 6AM
 - About 6.30AM
 - About 7AM
 - About 7.30AM
 - About 8AM
 - About 8.30AM
 - About 9AM
 - About 9.30AM
 - About 10AM
 - About 10.30AM
 - About 11AM
 - About 11.30AM
 - About 12PM
 - About 12.30PM
 - About 1PM
- (Between 4AM and 1PM)